

The Dangers of E-Tourism and Tourist Protection Methods

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Abstract

E-tourism is an important place among the dealers in the global tourism market and has become an imperative necessity imposed by the nature of tourism services, which has been reflected in the development of the tourism industry in light of the competition between the tourist destinations, e-tourism has contributed to reduce the costs of promotion and reduce the size of employment and make the tourist live experience of travel from When traveling in places where he wants to travel away from factors that could affect his choice in tourism agencies. Despite the positive aspects of e-tourism, there are several risks that this kind of tourism can cause. How can tourists be protected from the dangers of e-tourism? To answer this problem, we can present this paper through the following axes

Keywords: E-Tourism, Tourist Protection Methods

The first axis: What is e-tourism;

The second axis: the dangers of e-tourism and the methods of protecting tourists;

Introduction:

E-tourism is the largest part of the volume of e-commerce. In this regard, the best solutions and the latest electronic systems for tourism services have been developed and implemented in terms of working on e-marketing strategies to achieve outstanding performance that contributes to the development of the tourism system to support the global tourism competitiveness to attract tourists and tourism investments. Environment, investment climate and supporting industries for the travel and tourism sector. E-marketing in the field of tourism is one of the main reasons for the success of this drip in the first stage. Which led to a revolution in tourism activity and activities related to the transfer and distribution and development of programs and acquisitions, especially in informatics leads to reach the consumer with a clear message at an appropriate price such as the adoption of the external world to reach the tourist at the lowest possible prices in light of these data was formulated the following problem:

How to protect a tourist from the dangers of e-tourism?

The first axis: What is e-tourism

E-tourism is linked to e-commerce and constitutes the largest part of its size and contributes to it at a high rate, through the group of tourism services provided through the Internet, and the beginning of e-tourism back to 1990; with the emergence of (world wide web –WWW-) and the entry of the Internet in the global trade market, The emergence of the concept of e-tourism, and increase the spread of this concept and its various applications, several factors, most notably the high contribution of e-tourism in the total international electronic commerce, and the development of tourism product provided and the development of new tourism activities compatible with segments of tourists FH, as well as an increase in the value added of the tourism sector in the national economy.

The concept of e-tourism is a modern concept in the science of tourism which is strongly intertwined with the concept of e-commerce. They emphasized their definition of the use of electronic business in the field of travel and tourism and the use of Internet technologies to activate the work of tourist suppliers and access to more efficient facilities for tourism consumers.¹

e-Tourism is a tourist recommendation and planning application to assist users in the organization of leisure and tourist agenda. First, a recommender system offers the user a list of the city places that are likely of interest to the user. This list takes into account the user demographic classification; the user likes in former trips and the preferences for the current visit. Second, a planning module schedules the list of recommended

places according to their temporal characteristics as well as the user restrictions; that is the planning system determines how and when to realize the recommended activities. Having the list of recommended activities organized as an agenda (i.e., an executable plan) is a relevant characteristic that most recommender systems lack.ⁱⁱ

It is also known that these services provided by information technology and communication to achieve and promote tourism and hotel services across the various open networks and dependent on the principles and bases of e-trade m-tourism , and goes beyond the concept of even further, These include mobile tourism for portable electronic devices, and so on. Thus, information and communication technology is used by the collection of tourism companies from institutions, bodies, and individuals. This technology may be used in the construction and construction of tourism entities, which require the technological know-how of its visitors, In modern technology In modern tourism e-business and the Internet are used in the field of travel and tourism, in order to obtain more efficient facilities for suppliers and tourist consumers, so it is possible to name any tourist style as the You will see if new technologies are used in the presentation of its products, and providing them to tourists on the Internet. This includes all the tourist operations of the tourism program offers, booking and organizing the trips through the Internet and post-service services.

For tourism businesses, the Internet offers the potential to make information and booking facilities available to large numbers of tourists at relatively low costs. It also provides a tool for communication between tourism suppliers, intermediaries, as well as end-consumers. OECD (2000) revealed that the advent of Internet-based electronic commerce offers considerable opportunities for firms to expand their customer base, enter new product markets and rationalize their business. WTO (2001) also indicated that electronic business offers SMEs the opportunity to undertake their business in new and more cost-effective ways.ⁱⁱⁱ

Internet business revolutionized European tourism, not only by tourism industry reorganization but also by changing relations between business partners (table no. 1).^{iv}

Table no. 1: Interaction between tourism organization, consumers, and government

e-business	Organizations	Consumers	Government
Organizations	Extranets between hoteliers and tour operators	e-commerce application where consumers purchase tourist production and services or air tickets.	Managers interacting with government departments.
Consumers	Consumers registering their preferences on airline or hotel loyalty/executive clubs.	Consumers informing other consumers good or bad practice.	Consumers applying for visas, requesting maps and local destination information.
Government	Government informing hotels about food safety legislation or taxation.	Government informing consumers on regulation, visa or vaccination requirements.	Governments interacting in tourism policy matters or asking technical assistance through organizations such as World Tourism Organization.

Source: Buhalis, D., 2003. *E-tourism. Information technology for strategic tourism management*. England: Pearson Education Limited, pp. 42.

a. Benefits of e-tourism

he application of ICTs on the tourism industry suggests that e-tourism reflects the digitisation of all processes and value chains in the tourism, travel, hospitality and catering industries. At the tactical level, it includes e-commerce and applies ICTs for maximising the efficiency and effectiveness of the tourism organisation^v

The importance of e-tourism stems from the huge benefits offered by both tourism providers and tourists, which contribute to overcoming traditional barriers in typical tourism transactions.

- a. To reduce the cost of tourist services provided, the use of e-tourism will reduce the costs of tourism marketing.
- b. Facilitate the provision of information on which the tourism industry relies. Tourist services are characterized by highly variable products. Their quality can only be measured by experience and depends mainly on the tourist's confidence in the quality of tourism services.
- c. The ease of developing the tourist product and the emergence of new tourism activities in accordance with the different segments of tourists, and this through the opinion polls that can be used to know the new tourist directions and basic services and complementary needs of tourists.

B. Requirements for the application of e-tourism

Currently, travelers must visit manually multiple independent Web sites to plan their trip, register their personal information multiple times, spend hours or days waiting for response or confirmation, and make multiple payments by credit card. Consumers are discouraged by the lack of functionality. They are demanding the ability to create, manage and update itineraries. With dynamic packaging technology, travelers can build customized trips that combine customer preferences with flights, car rentals, hotel, and leisure activities in a single price.^{vi}

The application of e-tourism through social networking sites or the Internet is not aimed at gathering new people or specialists in the tourism industry. Commercial electronic transactions can only be achieved by providing a set of requirements, the most important of which are:

The organizational and institutional framework In order to increase the interest in the field of electronic arena, whether in the neighborhood or in the tourism itself, it is necessary to create an organizational and institutional framework that is at least continuous and continuous during the early stages of introducing electronic commerce systems in the work of tourist bodies And various tourist intermediaries.

B. The legal and legislative structure: The importance of the legislator issuing an e-commerce law that regulates the increasing electronic transactions in the recent period, and to provide in this law legislative texts pertaining to tourism activity in general and e-tourism in particular or at least its texts provide the full opportunity for the work of the tourist actors. Tourism legislation, and its compatibility with the requirements for the organization of electronic space, especially in the field of work of tourist agencies.

C - Supporting procedures These measures include adopting policies encouraging the use of Internet applications in tourism transactions by giving discounts on the prices of the customs of the different routes purchased through the Internet or granting the debt customers to make their reservations directly through the Internet additional number of free miles, or Give free registration to a certain number to be purchased by the customer from the web. And work on upgrading the existing tourist sites so that most of them enter the best one hundred thousand sites in the world.

It is possible to focus on the most used languages and provide real tourist data in a lucid and clear way for the browser through the Internet, and secure it to ensure the integrity of transactions and data Which may be traded through these sites.

D- International cooperation efforts: The tourism industry needs international cooperation. It is not enough to have the basic elements of a country or the availability of technological components to show e-tourism.

The second axis: the dangers of e-tourism and the methods of protecting tourists;

The conflict between travel and travel agencies and electronic booking systems through the Internet, with the huge growth in the use of the Internet until it reached the limit of competition in the spread of each of them influence the industry, which is the largest and largest industries in the world being one of the largest and most important sectors And with the development of technology there are dozens of risks, not because of a defect in new technology, but because of misuse and misuse, and electronic piracy. The

tourism sector, like all other sectors, is relying heavily on modern technology, and it has become a process of flying a hotel or hotel by telephone, but unfortunately there are some scammers did not leave the tourist congratulations, as a result of traps are mastered proficiently and robberies on the bank account that is used.^{vii}

1- The risks of e-tourism

E-tourism has a climate and also risks, and if we address these risks, we will find that the most important risks are the ease of control and direction of sale for a specific entity or a state or tourist area, which may affect tourism negatively to enter several factors that may be purely political or commercial damage to tourism , As well as the growth of cheap tourism, for the emergence of the shantytowns META to compare prices and thus tourism will fall prey to the price policy. Also, the risk of this tourism that the state will not be able to monitor the income of hotels and agencies so as to facilitate the manipulation of revenue to reduce taxes and maximize profit will address the most important of these negatives is the inability to control the information published and therefore difficult to account for the publisher of the lack of laws to reduce the dissemination of false information may Harms the State or the State in a direct or indirect manner.

2. Types of e-tourism risks ?:

The five major risks associated with tourism are "terrorism" (Richter, 2003), "war and political instability" (Sonmez, Apostolopoulos, & Tarlow, 1999), "health" (Richter, 2003), "crime" (Dimanche & Lepetic, 1999), and "cultural and language difficulties" (Basala&Klenosky, 2001). "These risks are of growing importance in the global tourism environment, and present threats not only to tourists but also host societies and the tourist's home nations" (Richter, 2003).^{viii}

a. The risks are detectable, and the intention here is that the agency and with the presence of specialized experts may be able to catch some of the breakthroughs in their systems and deal with them, and the most famous of these breakthroughs:

- Known digital viruses, with the existence of an appropriate protection system, the Agency's system can catch these viruses already known and eliminated.
- Hackers Internet hackers rely on hackers to hack information and access codes, so that the agency uses the mechanism to change those codes periodically, and scanning the memory concerned by experts will be able to scale penetration.

B - Risks cannot be detected, and what is meant here, that some breakthroughs may take place without prior knowledge, either to the Agency's ignorance or ignorance, and stems from the following reasons:

- Unknown viruses: Although there are virus protection systems on the systems of the agency, there are unknown viruses of the system may be able to enter the network system, and causing significant damage without feeling it until it is too late.

C. Internet hackers with high experience.

Dr. Technological acceleration It is often difficult to keep pace with technological acceleration on the Internet in general, and on e-commerce in particular, which makes the technology used by the company very old, and the problem is not knowing the statute of limitations in a timely manner.

e. Access from several places: The online client does not need a specific place to access the network, anyone who can access the network from anywhere with a computer and a line of communication.

1- Methods of protecting tourists from the dangers of e-tourism.

No doubt that tourists protection has as starting point the consumers. However, if we analyze this problem in terms of applicability, we will see two boundaries: the consumer rights protection on itself and protection on the obligations of providers in connection with carrying out duties.^{ix}

Some of the tourist protection techniques can be introduced from the risks of electric tourism:

a. Personal information is given by giving personal information only to trusted authorities and knowing the reasons for their need for such information. Personal information includes mainly postal address, telephone numbers, and e-mail.

B. It is also recommended when creating secret numbers. Stay away from traditional things by creating a number, such as using your name or phone number, and preferably making your number. The secret is somewhat complicated and is contained in a combination of numbers, letters, and symbols. The more secret your secret number is, the harder it is to discover.

C. Use of secured payment cards: It is preferable to use secured or protected payment cards. This means that online income card issuers, who have special policies that protect the customer from responsibility for the unauthorized use of his card by third parties, will be dealt with.

Dr. Capturing copies of operations: These are important things that contribute to the detection of thefts and avoid continuation

e. Check the company's website.

And. Use a secure program to access the Internet.

G. Anxiety of downloading online programs is not a reliable source.

H. Do not allow children to use the network without supervision.

Conclusion

In the light of the study, which dealt with the dangers of e-tourism and the methods of protecting the tourist, and the review and analysis of his role in the promotion of the tourism sector, it is possible to come up with some of the suggested recommendations, as follows:

- Establishment of electronic groups in English on Facebook to target new segments of Arab and foreign youth, and to familiarize them with the most important aspects of tourist excellence and how to organize tourist trips at reasonable prices to take into account the difference in priorities and prices.
- Send a monthly bulletin about the most important developments in the field of tourism (tourist offers from companies - Hotel prices - New facilities and pictures - Aviation services - Some articles and dialogues with officials and decision makers in the field of tourism.
- The need to pay attention to the dissemination of legal awareness while training cadres working in the field of tourism.
- Encouraging banks to develop small and medium-sized enterprises and tourism to develop manage and operate their activities using information technology and overcoming obstacles to obtaining the necessary funding so that the global variables will be forgotten.

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